

A Study on Slow Learner Children Education and Challenge

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Abstract

The slow learner student has been described in numerous ways Ingram-1960 considers them as educable mentally retarded child. This self-confidence has been well Plant in slow learner students for important there social life. Slow learner students have low self-confidence. One of the reasons for low self-esteem is discrimination and bullying at school slow learning children were pupils. Who by reasons of limited ability or other conditions resulting in educational retardation required some specialized form of education, wholly or partly in substitution for the education normally given in ordinary schools .These terminologies have less stigmatized effect. They are not based on medical or psychological categorization but purely on educational needs. The causes of the educational backwardness are: school absence, ill health unfavorable school and home conditions, and emotional barriers to learning The cause is not so much of limited ability. Therefore, these children need to suitable investment of educational environment in the institution. Slow learners children's to get every time we are encourage and the teacher also care to child. Slow learners do not understand the material taught by the teacher. The self-confidence analysis shows that all students are slow learners in the category have being confident. Slow learner children's need guidance and care all educational fields.

Keywords Skills, Learning Environment, Mantel Health, Parents Support.

Introduction

The term slow learner is frequently used to cover various groups of children otherwise referred to 'dull', 'retarded' or educationally subnormal. In the present circumstances it is used more widely to indicate the fairly large group of children whose learning is slowed down factors of which limited ability may be one. The common factor with all pupils seen was some measure of educational retardation, the contributing factor being manifold – cultural and poverty, family inadequacies, and parental disharmony. Pupil from such homes as these may well function as slow learner' even through their intellectual potential may be considerable higher. The slow learning is directly related to motivational and guidance activities. But resent studies in the regard revealed that heredity alone is not responsible for the backwardness of the children, but environment contribution significantly to the scholastic achievement of the child. The backward child is a slow learner he fined it difficult to keep pace with the normal child in his school works. Taking is also only I.Q. Into contribution, we cannot difference between a slow learner and average leaner child is his slow learner rate. At the discussion slow learner student not special education .in fact slow learners receive additional educational supportive services, in the regular classroom, curricular and learning. Some slow learners are not special education classroom or because they would otherwise fail in the regular classroom, even though they do not have special education needs. There is no diagnostic or descriptive profile that characteristic the slow learner. Slow learners are described by their specific academic weakness. During the last several years they has been increased interest in the education of slow learners, otherwise known as backward pupils in schools. In the classroom there is a need for prevention and treatment of backwardness whether they are in ordinary schools or in special education classes. The word 'slow learner children' is a broad generic term as stated by 'Tansley and Guilford, 1971'.

Objective of study

i. Special educations programmes need to provide education for slow learner's children from need to give concentration on general education.

- ii. Slow learners Children and on special needs of each individual child in daily living skill self help skills, academic skills and on communication skills.
- iii. A special programmed of education needs to try to coordinate disabilities of slow learner children with the general educational.
- iv. Objective of special education is to determine the special strength and weakness of slow learners' children and to facilitate courses of education for placement or for the fulfillment of their goals.

Review of Literature

The slow learner children's we are educational and environment improved in society. Many studies have been conducted on slow learners. The studies presented in this section deal with various aspects of slow learners.

Schoer (1962) in his study on the effect of list length and interpolated learning on the learning and recall of fast and slow learners proved that interpolated learning would not affect the recall of fast and slow learners significantly.

Stein** (1965) conducted a study on the IQ changes in educationally subnormal children at special schools and the study revealed that constancy of IQ is seen only in one third of the sample and in the remaining IQ changes sufficient to lift the child'en well into intellectual normality was identified.

Downing^ (1967) conducted a survey of teacher's report on the effect of the Initial Teaching Alphabet on educationally subnormal pupils. Initial Teaching Alphabets (I.T.A.) is useful to the slow learners since each word of English has only one print form in I.T.A. and the phonemes (sound units) of English have fewer representations in I.T.A. The survey revealed that I.T.A. is 75% Review of Related Literature very effective with subnormal children. The children showed positive attitude and increased raotivation in using I.T.A.

Shuell and Keppel^ (1970) studied the free recall performance of fast and slow learners and the results of the experiment indicated that fast and slow learners profit from additional study time to about the same extent and that the performance of the two groups is equivalent when the stimulus list is presented at a rate of 1 and 5 seconds respectively.

Parker (1972) conducted a study on the operant methods for teaching slow learning children sequential motor tasks using the methods developed by the investigator himself. The method incorporated chaining and sequencing of the elements of behavior. The method was found useful in teaching slow learning students sequential motor tasks.

Isakson and Miller' (1976) compared good and poor comprehenders on the basis of the sensitivity to syntactic and semantic cues and the study revealed that the poor comprehenders are not affected by the disruptive effect of syntactic and semantic violations.

Saracho and Dayton*** (1980) analyzed the relationship of teachers' cognitive style to pupils' academic achievement gains. The study indicated 16% Review of Related Literature significant effects on academic gains of students due to teacliars' cognitive style.

John (1982) conducted a study on the effect of finger mathematics or chisanbop upon the Mathematic computational ability and Mathematical attitude of month grade general m^athematics slow learners with attention given to the variables of sex and learning styles. The study revealed that finger math does not enhance math computation ability.

Singh (1983) compared the high and low academic achievers in self concept formation and the study revealed that there is a positive significant relation between self-concept and academic achievement.

Sodhi*** (1989) conducted a study on the emotional problems in minority group and caste Hindu children and their level of achievement motivation and scholastic achievements and the study revealed that emotional problem is negatively correlated to achievement to a significant degree.

Manjula^(1990) analyzed the impact of certain teaching skills on the achievement of underachievers at the primary stage and the study revealed that the underachievers who

were taught with the use of teaching skills achieved higher in comparison with those taught without the use of teaching skills.

Raju[^] (1991) studied the cognitive outcomes in secondary school biology of low and high affective achievers. The study revealed that all the 77 Review of Related Literature cognitive variables significantly discriminated between high affective achievers and low affective achievers.

Satia (1992), in his study on the Socio-psychological and educational factors of differential learning rate in modern Mathematics at the senior secondary stage, found that the intellectual level of rapid and average learners, SES of slow learners personality traits of rapid average and slow learner correlated significantly with their achievement in modern mathematics. Rapid, average and slow learners differed significantly in their intellectual and SES levels.

Peggy (1994) studied two poor reader groups (dyslexia and slow learning) and a normal reading group with attention deficit disorder (ADD). In correlational analyses, the combination of greater low beta and less theta power significantly predicted better reading and spelling. Results suggest adequate readers process stimuli more actively than the poor readers.

Helmut^{''} (1995) studied the characteristics of the disadvantaged youth who leave school without vocational qualifications, as well as unskilled 20-30 year olds and the study revealed that a combination of work and initial vocational training is the best strategy to deal with disadvantaged children. Constant supportive counselling and adapted examinations would also help.

Rao and Rajaguru[^] (1995) studied the effectiveness of video assisted instruction on the achievement of slow learners. The study revealed that the female slow learners of video assisted instruction group performed better in immediate retention than conventional learning group. The video assisted instruction facilitated male and female slow learners to have better retention even after the lapse of one month period.

Reddy and Ramar (1995) conducted a study on effectiveness of multimedia instructional strategy in teaching science to slow learners. The study revealed that multimedia instructional strategy helps the slow learner perform in a better fashion in Science.

Reddy and Ramar^{^^} (1996) studied the effectiveness of video instruction in teaching science and social science to slow learners. There was significant difference between the pre-test and the post-test mean scores of experimental group slow learners when science was taught through video instruction and their achievement was higher in the post-test than in the pretest. The slow learners taught through traditional method group and the slow learners taught through the experimental method also showed significant difference. The achievement of the slow learners taught using video instruction was higher than the achievement of control group slow learners.

Reddy and Ramar^{^*} (1996) studied the effectiveness of Multimedia based modular approach in teaching English to slow learners. The study revealed that there is significant difference between the pre- test and the posttest mean scores of the experimental group slow learners when English is taught through multimedia based modular approach. Their achievement was higher in the post-test than in the pre- test. There is significant difference between the post-test mean scores of the control group slow learners taught through the traditional lecture method and the experimental group slow learners taught through multimedia based modular approach.

Reddy and Rainar (1996) studied the effectiveness of video instruction on achievement of slow learners in Mathematics. There was significant difference between the pre-test and the post-test mean scores of experimental group slow learners when Mathematics was taught through video instruction and their achievement was higher in the post-test than in the pretest. The rate of progress made by the experimental group slow learners was higher than that of the control group slow learners.

Reddy and Ramar^{^^} (1997) studied the effect of Modular Approach on achievement of slow learners in Social Science. There was significant difference between the pre-test and the post-test mean scores of experimental group slow learners when Social Science was taught through Modular Approach and their achievement was higher in the post-test than in the pre-test. The achievement of the slow learners taught using Modular Approach was higher than the achievement of control group slow learners.

Reddy and Ramar[^] (1997) studied the effectiveness of Multimedia instructional strategy in teaching Science to slow learners. The study revealed that there is significant difference between the pre- test and the post-test mean scores of the experimental group slow learners when science is taught through multimedia instructional strategy. Their achievement was higher in the post-test than in the pre- test. There is significant difference between the post-test mean scores of the control group slow learners taught through the traditional lecture method and the experimental group slow learners taught through multimedia instructional strategy. The achievement of experimental group slow learners was higher than the control group slow learners.

Shaji^{^^} (1997) studied the impact of interventional materials on the achievement of slow learners from the 4th standard of Mysore city. The study 80 Review of Related Literature revealed that the intend 'educational materials greatly influenced the achievement of slow learners.

Kaznowsky (2003) conducted a study on the educabihty of slow learners. The study revealed that slow learners are not successful in school and hence the investigator suggested vocational education.

Tiramermans and Lieshout^{^"} (2003) studied the influence of instruction in Mathematics for low performing students on strategy use. The stiidy highlighted the need for constructivist teaching style in Mathematics for low perfonning students.

Birch and Guy^{^^} (2004) conducted a study on the effect of phonological processing automaticity and auditory processing of the memory in slow learners and children with reading disabilities. Follow up comparison found that slow learners had significantly poorer perfonnance in comparison with control group after the intervention

Kaznowski and Kimberly^{^^} (2004) conducted a study to determine which group of slow learners was more successful in school in order to know if special education or regular education is the most beneficial educational "placement" for the slow learners. Findings suggest that neither group of slow learners is successful in school; both are doing remarkably poorly. Educational alternatives are required to prevent slow learners from continuing to fall through the cracks

Krishnakumar et.al.^{^^"} (2004), conducted a study on self esteem and the study showed that children had significant improvement in their academic functioning and self esteem after the training. The present experiment can be a model to set up a resource room in normal schools to provide individualized education to children who are slow learners.

Silver et.al/^{/"} (2006) in this study, the author discusses how technologies such as text-to-speech, speech recognition, graphic organizers, 81 Review of Related Literature and e-resources can be integrated into sound pedagogy to help struggling slow learners achieve both academic and technological success.

Curtis and Shaver (2008) attempted to improve the self esteem of slow learners of the secondary social science classes. The important finding of the study is that the most striking quality of slow learners is low self-esteem. This paper reports the findings of the study designed to increase the self-esteem of slow learners in social studies classes in a number of secondary schools in British Columbia, Canada. Students in the control classes followed the prescribed social studies programme.

Leff Rhona (2008), carried out a study on the needs of teachers to "tricks up their sleeves" for working with slow learners. The study initiates a staff-development plan for changing that. The study also presents some suggestions for using the time, resources, and staff to improve the teaching of Slow learners.

Warnemuende (2008) conducted a study on helping parents to help their struggling children in learning. The investigator found out that parents of struggling learners are often unsure of how to assist their children at home. The investigator provides useful strategies and tips for principals to help parents support and encourage their children who are slow learners.

Astalini et al., 2020; Suryani & Gunawan, 2018-. Because Indonesia wants to strengthen its character to compete in this digital era. However, in the world of education, not all students have high self-confidence. One of the students who have low self-confidence is a slow learner. Slow learner students have low self-confidence and abstract thinking skills.

Ahmad et al., 2015; Mami & Arayesh, 2010- Teachers and friends often underestimate slow learner students. It is what causes slow learner students to have low self-confidence.

Slow learner students have limitations in understanding the material/L. D. Pratama & Setyaningrum, 2018-.Slow learner students need several repetitions to understand the material. Slow learner students are physically no different from ordinary students. In addition, slow learners thinking skills are lower than children in general, which causes them to be less confident, look embarrassed, have difficulty interacting and socializing /(Ellis et al., 2021; Shokoohi-Yekta et al., 2011).

Slow learner students did not show any difference from ordinary students. In addition, slow learner students also have limitations in language, communication, and expressing their emotions F. I. P. Pratama et al., 2021; Vita, 2016 - Based on the observations of elementary schools in Kudus Regency, it was found that teachers still do not understand the characteristics of slow learner students, teachers tend to give the same treatment to their students in learning activities, in learning teachers do not use learning media, besides that teachers tend to focus on intelligent students. Meanwhile, based on the results of observations to students, it was found that slow learner students felt ignored by the teacher, slow learner students did not understand the material taught by the teacher, slow learner students tended to be silent and looked down on when learning.

Slow learner students do not dare to come forward, and it is not easy to express their opinions (Otache et al., 2021; F. I. P. Pratama et al., 2021)-If allowed to continue will harm his development in the future. Therefore, teachers need to know how to help slow learner students based on their abilities. Furthermore, self-confidence is essential in one's personality, prolonged learner students. Self-confidence is necessary to be instilled in slow learner students for not lacking in their abilities, being more trusted for themselves among others, and improving their skills in solving problems.

Franz et al., 2020; Mulyono & Saskia, 2020.Slow learners students in low confidence will have difficulty exploration, have low performance, and the worst thing is that they donot have long-term goals

Alvarez et al., 2021; Shokoohi-Yekta et al., 2011.Physical point of view, slow learner children do not show different characteristics from ordinary students. Slow learner children are limited to academic abilities and other abilities such as language or communication, emotional, social, or moral aspects, short attention span.

Methodology

Educationists as well as psychologists have conducted many experiments to devise special methods of teaching for slow learners. Their results indicate that the slow learners require short and simple methods of instruction based on concrete experiences. Verbal instructions should be limited.

Result and Discussion

In a classroom there must be some slow learners. These children consist of a group with mild handicaps. They come to school regularly. From the psychological

Point of view, it would be conducive for these children to be identified earlier. Then necessary step can taken to help them in their learning. A teaching expert is easily able to identify and deviation in classroom behavior pertaining to learning difficulties of children. He has primary knowledge about the more important when spells out clearly that the slow learners more help to acquire the skills in comparison with children. These children also reply more on concrete leaning rather than abstract learning psychologists and experts use various tools and techniques to identify slow learner. These are as follow-

Observation Technique- This observation may be done under simple as well as controllable conditions. Observation of children's behaviour by the teacher as well as experts may help in identifying slow learners. A child's behaviour is not only observation in the classroom, but also on the playground, home and in the group etc. observation may be done by just watching the child's behaviour directly and by moving along with the child. It should be kept in mind that for this technique is information has gets from his observation. Observations technique is conducive for ascertaining the recreational, occupation and extracurricular interest of children.

Medical examination- The developmental history from early childhood should be meticulously verified by qualified medical expert or medical practitioner. Under strict physical and medical examination, the anomalies can also be evaluated properly.

Personality test- The slow learners children should be designed with sensitivity and patience. They should focus on understanding their strengths, challenges and development milestones as like social skills, emotional regulation and interest to provide. Through personality tests, attempts can be making by psychologists to throw light on the emotional characteristics of children as well as temperamental traits. Evidence shows that there are certain personality traits which direct relationship with specific backwardness persistence, sensitiveness, concentration, emotional stability, assertiveness. Etc.

Physical activities- There are three groups of children who are show to develop both mentally and physically and three appears to be a slow growth potential resulting in all round immaturity. Whose capacity to learn is reduced because of sickness, minor ailments, malnutrition. They need feelings of success and confidence and improved social development. Many ENS children have better physical development than mental development.

Weakness of attention- one cause poor memory is wekness in attention. These children are restless and destructible. Attention may be poor because of mismatched or irrelevant materials .the methods presenting learning materials may not facilitate accurate perception of it. The teacher must therefore pay special attention to getting children to see links which briter children would probably see for themselves various sensory modalities can be used to present the links and associations. For example the word `night` can the first sequence of letters

n-i-g-h-t. Then visual displaying, speaking. Asking him to write down, linking it with light, sight, pight.

Intelligent test – Through the use of any standardized intelligence test and non-verbal tests can be used for that purpose. But psychologists prefer individual verbal test to group verbal test. Designing an intelligent for slow learner involves several consideration, it should be structured to accommodate different learning paces and styles, should focus on assessing understanding rather than speed, incorporating visuals , hand-on activities, and real-life scenarios can enhance comprehension, providing supportive feedback and encouragement throughout the test can boost confidence and motivation. An expert can get a true picture of the mental capacities of backward children by giving many intelligence tests.

Feeling of insecurity- slow learning children have a feeling of insecurity which arise out of personal inadequacy physical or mental. They are unable to control feeling of aggression or outbursts. The ENS children continuously seek attention and approval of the teacher. They do experience the need for acceptance from the peer groups .the isolated child may withdraw still further.

Scholastic Tests:- Evaluation of the slow learner likely refer to assessments designed to measure the academic abilities of student who may require additional support or accommodation due to learner difficulties . Evaluation or deficiencies in school achievement can be possible through scholastic tests. These test can throw light on areas like arithmetic, reading, spelling, composition, writing, language and comprehension .These tests aim identify areas of strength and weakness to better educational inventions and supports for the student. General and specific problems of children are psychologists through scholastic tests, singled out by anomalies can also be evaluated properly.

Flexible curriculum- Educationist may take care in preparing the curriculum for slow learners which should be flexible as possible to suit and need of the every individual student slow learner are generally interested in concrete perceptual experiences to the children and attention must be paid towards among the student.

Conclusion

Based on the research results, teachers still do not understand the characteristics of slow learner students, and teachers tend to give the same treatment as students in general. Teachers do not use learning media, and teachers focus on intelligent students. In addition, slow learner students feel that the teacher does not care, slow learner students do not understand the material taught by the teacher, slow learner students tend to be silent and look down when learning. The self-confidence analysis shows that all students are slow learners in the category of not being confident. The slow learner children always need better helps from formal education and good environmental for the every situation on life. Slow learner student in the diagnosis, treatment and research cooperation between teachers, doctors, psychologists. Administrators and social workers are vital role of every person of society. The psychologist can make a contribution by providing a detailed picture

of the children personality, discovering in the development of emotional and mental health. On Perceptual and conceptual difficulties, intellectual strength and weakness emotional abnormalities of the slow learner students by guidance from school, institution and other psychological test help of the slow learner children in our society.

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